

Kinetics of Saponification of Unsaturated Esters in Aqueous DMSO

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The kinetics of alkaline hydrolysis of a representative group of unsaturated esters have been studied in binary solvent mixtures of DMSO-water and ethanol-water. In a few selected cases, the corresponding saturated analogues have also been investigated. The observed order of reactivity among the various unsaturated esters studied are best explained in terms of the inductive and conjugative effects of the unsaturated group present in the ester. The saponification rates are much higher in aqueous DMSO compared to aqueous ethanol. The existence of a structural effect *vis-a-vis* solvent effect in these systems is analysed.

As part of our investigations on the kinetics of saponification of esters in aqueous dipolar aprotic solvents and in continuation of our earlier report¹, we have studied the kinetics of a few typical unsaturated esters as also their saturated analogues in mixtures of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)-water and ethanol-water and the results are presented in this communication. The information available on these type of substrates is limited²⁻⁴, more so with respect to the solvent effects of these reactions.

Experimental

Commercial samples of the esters (extra pure variety, Fluka AG/BDH) were used in the kinetic runs after purification by distillation. DMSO (Crown Zellerbach Corporation, USA) was purified by distillation under reduced pressure while pure ethanol was prepared from commercial rectified spirit by standard procedures. The rate measurements were carried out by titrimetric procedures using a screened indicator composed of neutral red and methylene blue and the velocity constants were calculated from the integrated rate equations.

Results and Discussion

Unsaturation in the acyl group :

The representative compounds studied under this category include ethyl acrylate and ethyl crotonate and their saturated analogues—ethyl propionate and ethyl butyrate. The kinetics of saponification of methyl acrylate, methyl methacrylate, ethyl cinnamate, *p*-nitro ethyl cinnamate and benzyl cinnamate have also been studied. The rate data for the alkaline hydrolysis of these esters in varying compositions of aqueous DMSO and aqueous ethanol (v/v) are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF UNSATURATED ESTERS IN AQUEOUS DMSO(v/v)

Ester	Temp: 30°		
	60% DMSO	70% DMSO	80% DMSO
Ethyl acrylate	17.70	21.40	33.00
Ethyl propionate	...	20.30	...
Ethyl crotonate	2.42	3.07	5.35
Ethyl butyrate	8.88	11.70	14.80
Methyl acrylate	...	76.70	...
Methyl methacrylate	19.70	27.70	48.70
Ethyl cinnamate	7.63
Benzyl cinnamate	20.40	26.10	53.80

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TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF UNSATURATED ESTERS IN AQUEOUS ETHANOL (v/v)

Ester	Temp : 30°		
	60% EtOH	70% EtOH	80% EtOH
Ethyl acrylate	1.930	1.430	1.070
Ethyl propionate	...	1.290	...
Ethyl crotonate	0.240	0.172	0.136
Ethyl butyrate	0.771	0.568	0.486
Methyl acrylate	...	1.900	...
Methyl methacrylate	0.859	0.646	0.456
Ethyl cinnamate	0.492
Benzyl cinnamate	0.527	0.393	0.286
<i>p</i> -Nitro ethyl cinnamate	3.330

The cumulative influence of two opposing factors lead to near identical reactivity of the pair ethyl acrylate and ethyl propionate in both solvent systems. While the electronegative nature of the α : β unsaturation present in ethyl acrylate would increase its reactivity towards alkaline hydrolysis (by a B_{AC}² mechanism), conjugation of the double bond with the carbonyl function of the ester tends to bring down its rate of hydrolysis. However, with the introduction of a β -methyl group as in ethyl crotonate, the rate retarding conjugation prevails over the -I effect of the unsaturated group. Thus ethyl crotonate is hydrolysed much slower than its saturated analogue—ethyl butyrate. This situation is true for the different solvent systems and solvent compositions employed.

The observed order of reactivity between ethyl cinnamate and ethyl crotonate can be traced to the strongly electron withdrawing nature of the phenyl group on the β -carbon atom. The conjugation with the carbonyl group, of course, reduces the reactivity of ethyl cinnamate when compared to ethyl acetate in both the solvents (the rate constants for the alkaline hydrolysis of ethyl acetate at 30° in 60% DMSO and 60% EtOH are 27.4×10^{-2} and 2.71×10^{-2} litre mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ respectively). The resonance concept thus provides a rational explanation of the fact that the rates of alkaline hydrolysis of normal benzoates, cinnamates, crotonates etc. are very appreciably slower than the corresponding acetates⁵. This effect holds on in spite of the fact that the substituents involved are, relative to the methyl group, moderately strong electron

withdrawing groups. Further these substituents normally produce only small steric effects, so that substantially slower rates may not be attributed to this cause.

The strong-I effect of the phenyl group is reflected in the enhanced rates of hydrolysis of benzyl cinnamate over ethyl cinnamate. The rate enhancement is, however, much higher in aqueous DMSO. This can be traced to a 'DMSO catalysis' of aromatic systems and this has been described by us earlier¹. The increased rate of hydrolysis of *p*-nitro ethyl cinnamate over the parent compound in aqueous ethanol (as also its immeasurably faster rate of hydrolysis in aqueous DMSO) is in accord with the rate-enhancing influence of a *p*-nitro group in hydrolysis proceeding by the B_{AC}² mechanism.

The value of the rate constant decreases with increase in the size of the alkyl group of the acrylates (cf. methyl acrylate and ethyl acrylate). This rate drop is much higher in aqueous DMSO than in aqueous ethanol of the same organic content, as in the case of the corresponding acetate esters⁷.

The effect of methyl substitution on the acyl portion, near the reaction centre, is brought out in the case of methyl methacrylate. The retardation of the rate of hydrolysis when a hydrogen atom on the α -carbon atom is replaced by a methyl group is comparable in the case of methyl acrylate and methyl methacrylate and ethyl propionate and ethyl isobutyrate² (3 times).

Unsaturation in the alkyl group :

The effect of unsaturation on alkyl group has been studied choosing allyl acetate as the typical substrate. The replacement of the electron releasing methyl group in ethyl acetate by an electron withdrawing vinyl group in allyl acetate produces a rate enhancement which is, however, not very pronounced, the unsaturation being away from the reaction centre (Table 3).

Temp: 30°	10 ² k litre	mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
Ester	70% DMSO	70% EtOH
Ethyl acetate	32.5	2.11
Allyl acetate	60.9	3.37

Solvent influences :

The general expectation of a rate enhancement, when the ethanol content of the solvent system is replaced by DMSO, has been realised in the present studies also. Increasing DMSO concentration in DMSO-water mixtures increases the rates of saponification while the reverse trend is true of increasing ethanol content in the solvent mixtures.

Both solvent systems give rise to good linear plots of log *k* versus 1/*D* for all the esters studied (*D* being the dielectric constant of the medium). The negative slopes of these plots for ethanol-water mixtures, on treatment with the Amis equation⁸, lead to reasonable values for the parameter 'r' representing the radius of the transition state. The positive slopes for the plots for DMSO-water mixtures, however, fail to respond to the above treatment in as much as they do not lead

to reasonable values for the parameter 'r' demonstrating the inadequacy of the use of dielectric constant as a criterion of solvent effects in DMSO-water mixtures. This is quite in keeping with our earlier observations.

The rate enhancements in DMSO-water mixtures are to be traced to the cumulative effect of two factors (i) the presence of a highly desolvated and hence an active OH⁻ ion in these solvent mixtures and (ii) the capacity of DMSO to solvate effectively the transition state for these reactions⁹.

The extent to which the rate differs for methyl and ethyl acrylates in the two solvent systems is in conformity with Parker and Ko's concept of 'loose' and 'tight' transition states¹⁰ and the influence of the two solvent systems on these types of transition states. According to this postulate, as applied to a S_N² reaction involving an anion, increasing alkylation around the reaction centre would lead to 'loosening' up of the transition state of the reaction and consequently to an increase in its solvation by the protic solvent. Conversely a less crowded and hence 'tighter' transition state would be preferentially solvated by an aprotic solvent. In the present instance, it follows, therefore, that replacement of a methyl group by an ethyl group should have less pronounced effects on the rates of hydrolysis in aqueous ethanol. This is indeed what is observed. This picture of transition state solvation is more elegantly demonstrated in the saponification of alkyl acetates⁷.

The most curious situation of solvent effects *vis-a-vis* structural effects in the present studies is met with in the case of methyl methacrylate and ethyl acrylate—esters differing by the position of an extra methyl group in methyl acrylate molecule—in the acyl portion or the alkyl portion. The comparison of the rate data for the alkaline hydrolysis of these esters in 70% aqueous DMSO, a typical aprotic medium, in 70% aqueous ethanol, a typical protic solvent system and in pure water³ which represents a transition between these two types, is revealing (Table 4).

Temp : 30°	10 ³ k litre	mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	
Ester	70% DMSO	*water	70% EtOH
Methyl acrylate	767	198.0	190.00
Methyl methacrylate	277	83.0	6.46
Ethyl acrylate	214	102.0	14.30

* from ref. 3

As the aprotic nature of the solvent system increases, the difference in reactivity between methyl methacrylate and ethyl acrylate decreases and is even reversed in 70% DMSO. This reversal is extraordinary in that the substituent effects in ester saponifications are known to be more pronounced when the substituent is in the acyl portion of the ester and accordingly methyl methacrylate ought to react slower than ethyl acrylate as is indeed the case in aqueous ethanol.

The observed solvent effects on the deactivating power of the methyl group at the two positions in methyl acrylate can be traced to the differences of charge distribution at the actual reaction centre or in other words on the 'looseness' or 'tightness' of the transition states for the saponification of these esters. It is likely that the electron releasing resonance effect of the unsaturated group is compensated by the hyperconjugative release of electrons by the methyl group in the opposite direction in methyl methacrylate. The absence of such a compensating influence would lead to a greater localisation of the negative charge on the carbonyl oxygen in the transition state for the hydrolysis of ethyl acrylate. In other words, the transition state for ethyl acrylate hydrolysis can be said to have become a 'loose' one, being favoured by a protic solvent ethanol. The comparatively 'tighter' transition state for methyl methacrylate hydrolysis stands to gain in an aprotic solvent like DMSO.

It is pertinent to point out here that Parker and Ko have observed a similar differentiating effect of solvents on the rate enhancing influences of *p*-methoxy and *p*-nitro substituents in benzyl bromide-azide ion reactions¹⁰. The *p*-nitro substituent is more effective in an aprotic solvent DMF while a *p*-methoxy substituent with a 'loose' transition state is more effective in a protic solvent methanol. It is not difficult to conceive of a parallel situation in the present instance, with the alkyl groups carrying the methyl group at two different positions behaving as two different substituents in methyl acrylate and exhibiting varying degrees of rate-retarding influence in the various solvent systems.

These observations incidentally demonstrate the greater role played by the 'transition state solvation' factor in rate enhancements of ester saponifications on transfer from a protic to a dipolar aprotic solvent.

References

1. M. BALAKRISHNAN, G. VENKOBA RAO and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 566.
2. E. A. HALOIVEN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 485.
3. R. C. SHARMA and M. M. SHARMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1970, **43**, 642.
4. C. G. EVANS and J. D. R. THOMAS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **B**, 1502.
5. R. W. TAFT JR., *Separation of polar, steric and resonance effects*, page 556 in reference 6.
6. M. S. NEWMAN., *Steric effects in organic chemistry*, John Wiley and Sons, N. Y., 1956.
7. M. BALAKRISHNAN., G. VENKOBA RAO and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, (communicated).
8. E. S. AMIS., *Solvent effects on reaction rates and mechanism*. Academic Press, N. Y., 1966.
9. A. J. PARKER., *Chem. Revs.*, 1969, **69**, 1.
10. A. J. PARKER and E. C. F. KO., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 6447.